

Tensions in the adoption of CoARA within the Spanish scientific system: a qualitative approach

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The implementation of CoARA represents one of the most recent developments in research assessment reform. However, little is known about how these reforms are being interpreted and applied in practice within specific national systems. This study draws on interviews with policy makers and researchers from the Spanish scientific system to examine how ongoing changes in evaluation practices are perceived and implemented. Our findings indicate that reform does not simply replace existing evaluation practices but leads to the coexistence of different assessment logics, generating tensions during the transition toward new evaluation frameworks. We present two of the main preliminary tensions identified in the interviews (metrics vs. qualitative judgement; traditional merits versus alternative forms of recognition) and outline future directions for the analysis.

1. Introduction

Research assessment has become a highly contested topic due to the influence that evaluation systems exert on researchers' careers, research agendas and the implementation of Open Science, amongst many other aspects (Gläser & Laudel, 2016; Arroyo-Machado & Torres-Salinas, 2026). As early as the 1980s, researchers warned against the misuse of metrics and an overreliance on publication-based metrics for research evaluation (Moed et al., 1985), as they can have detrimental consequences for the scientific system (Oravec, 2019), shape knowledge production (Rushforth & de Rijcke, 2015), and fail to account for the impact of research beyond academia (Ravenscroft et al., 2017).

At the same time, research evaluation systems do not operate as technical tools for measuring performance, but as institutional mechanisms of governance that structure academic careers, define research priorities and influence the allocation of recognition and resources. For this reason, debates about research assessment are not only methodological, but also institutional and epistemic in nature. Previous studies have described these dynamics in terms of "evaluation regimes" or "cultures of evaluation", highlighting how metrics, peer review practices and institutional incentives co-produce particular forms of knowledge production (Gläser & Laudel, 2016; Rijcke et al., 2016). In this sense, reforms in research assessment should not only be understood as technical adjustments to indicators, but as broader institutional transformations affecting how scientific value is defined and recognized (Saenen et al., 2019).

In response to these concerns, recent years have seen the proliferation of manifestos and initiatives calling for changes in research assessment. Particularly relevant are the Leiden Manifesto (Hicks et al., 2015) and the Declaration on Research Assessment of San Francisco

(DORA) (DORA, 2012). These initiatives highlighted the need for new approaches to research assessment, emphasizing qualitative judgement and responsible interpretation of evidence, rather than the misuse of decontextualized quantitative metrics. However, these initiatives established normative principles and recommendations rather than binding institutional commitments.

It is in this context that the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) emerged. Rather than introducing entirely new ideas, CoARA brings together and operationalizes many of these previous initiatives within a coordinated framework for reforming research assessment practices. The coalition proposes moving away from the almost exclusive reliance on isolated publication-based metrics and introducing a more nuanced system that recognizes the diversity of research outputs and academic career profiles (CoARA, 2022). Importantly, within the field of bibliometrics, quantitative indicators have long been conceived as tools to inform and support expert judgement, rather than as substitutes for qualitative evaluation.

CoARA was launched in 2022 at the European level, and it is mandatory for all institutions that sign it to create an action plan in which they commit to aligning their evaluation systems with the principles of the coalition. In order to facilitate this and given the heterogeneous nature of research assessment across the different European countries, the coalition created the so-called ‘national chapters’. These were designed to provide a shared direction for reform while preserving institutional autonomy and the diversity of national research systems, allowing institutions from the same country to meet and coordinate their efforts according to their specific context (CoARA, n.d.).

However, the transition toward these new evaluation principles does not necessarily imply the replacement of existing practices, but rather the coexistence of different evaluative logics during the process of implementation. Understanding how these logics interact in practice, and what tensions emerge from their coexistence, becomes particularly relevant for analysing how research assessment reforms are being interpreted and implemented within specific national systems.

2. Background and purpose

The idea that research assessment needs to change is a long-standing topic of debate amongst researchers (e.g. Narin, 1976, Nature, 2022). In recent years, some proposals have studied the possibility of having a more qualitative approach to scientific assessment, including using narrative CVs (Bordignon et al, 2023), or questioning how to fix the overloaded peer review system (Adam, 2025). CoARA aims at bringing together many of these proposals into a coordinated framework for reforming research assessment. The ten core principles of CoARA emphasize the recognition of diverse research contributions and careers paths, focusing more on qualitative evaluation (such as peer review) rather than inappropriate or isolated use of journal and publication-based metrics (such as the impact factor of journals) and rankings. Importantly, these principles do not imply the elimination of quantitative indicators, but rather their use in combination with expert judgement and contextual evaluation practices. Moreover, signatory institutions are expected to dedicate resources to implementing these reforms (CoARA, 2022).

Signatories of the agreement need to define an action plan on how they are going to implement the principles of the coalition either by the end of 2023, or one year after signing the agreement. Moreover, by the end of 2027 or five years after signing the agreement, they must demonstrate

progress towards their CoARA-aligned goals (CoARA, 2022). Given the recent creation of the coalition and, consequently, its adoption by institutions, most signatories are still designing their action plans or at very early stages of their implementation. Therefore, much of the existing literature is speculative and has focused on discussing the potential implications and challenges of CoARA or on criticising the potential pitfalls of it (e.g. Abramo, 2024). As stated by Rushforth (2025), such literature examining the ambiguities and dysfunctions of research evaluation systems is important, but there is an area that has not been studied enough: the one that examines research assessment reforms as they are implemented in practice. The relevance of this line of research is reflected in sessions such as “Implementing research assessment reforms: Tales from the frontline”, held at STI 2023 (Pölönen et al., 2023).

Pölönen & Rushforth (2025) carried out a study that overviews the signing of CoARA amongst the different European institutions and countries. They find that, as of August 2025, 13% of Higher Education Institutions from across Europe have signed CoARA, most of them being PhD awarding institutions. More than half of the universities in the Leiden ranking have signed it as well (51.8%), and the authors find a relationship between meta-organizations of research institutions and participation in CoARA. They find that those countries with the largest share of signing institutions are Finland, Sweden, Spain, Ireland and Norway (Pölönen & Rushforth, 2025), and they find lower support in Eastern European countries. This strong national clustering of engagement suggests that each national system has their own specificities, which makes national-level analyses particularly relevant for understanding how CoARA is interpreted and implemented.

This research focuses specifically on the Spanish research system. The Spanish scientific system is relatively centralized, and the National Evaluation and Accreditation Agency (ANECA) is the responsible institution for providing faculty accreditation—an evaluation required to apply for academic positions in Spanish public universities—and for the accreditation of academic programmes. The ANECA is also in charge of the so-called *sexenios*: six-year voluntary evaluation period that, if positive, translates into salary bonuses and other benefits (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2024; ANECA, n.d.). The ANECA has recently adopted the principles of CoARA for the *sexenios*, with observable effects on data, such as an increase in Green Open Access adoption across researchers (Arroyo-Machado & Torres-Salinas, 2026). According to Molas-Gallart (2024), for CoARA to be successful in this national scenario, there needs to be a change at the governance system level, which is something that more decentralised systems may not need.

In this study, we aim to explore how CoARA is being interpreted and implemented within the Spanish scientific system. We use qualitative methodologies that show the current perceptions and tensions that arise in this country during the application of CoARA in different institutions. This study examines how different evaluative logics coexist and generate tensions during the transitions toward new assessment frameworks. By interviewing both policy makers and researchers from higher education institutions and research centres, both public and private, across the country, we explore the following question: what tensions emerge in the implementation of CoARA across different actors within the Spanish research system?

3. Data and methods

3.1 In-depth interviews

To carry out the analysis we have performed in-depth interviews with policy makers (17) and researchers (19) from across the Spanish scientific system, from July 2025 to December 2025. Interviews lasted between 35-55 minutes and were conducted usually by two of the researchers,

although occasionally by one. They were carried out online, the audio was recorded and transcribed afterwards. The analysis was conducted in NVivo to systematically identify patterns and emerging themes in the data. Coding decisions and theme development were discussed among the research team to ensure consistency.

We followed two different approaches for selecting interviewees, one for policy makers (Table 1) and another for researchers (Figure 1), taking into account a range of relevant variables.

Table 1: Number of policy makers interviewed, given gender and institution

	Public University	Private University	Spanish public research organization	Other Research Center	Other funding bodies	Total
Women	2	1	3	6	1	13
Men	3	1	0	0	0	4
Total	5	2	3	6	1	17

Figure 1. Percentage of researchers interviewed, given type of institution (A), discipline (B), job category (C), location of institution (D) and gender (E).

3.2 Thematic analysis

We analyse the results of the interviews using thematic analysis, that is, ‘a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data’ (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This is a flexible method that allows us to interpret the data following six phases: A) familiarizing ourselves with the data, B) generating initial codes, C) searching for themes, D) reviewing themes, E) defining and naming themes and F) producing a final report (Braun & Clarke, 2006). At the time of the writing, the work is in step C and D, and we expect to be in step E or F by the time of the conference.

4. Preliminary results

This section explores how researchers and policy makers perceive the ongoing transformation of research evaluation systems and the tensions emerging from their implementation. Among

researchers, our results suggest, in general terms, a limited awareness of the theoretical and policy framework associated with the reform of research assessment promoted by CoARA, in line with the findings of previous research (Rousseau & Daraio, 2025). However, this conceptual unfamiliarity does not imply an absence of perceived change. On the contrary, many researchers identify ongoing transformations in evaluation practices, particularly when they participate in specific procedures such as accreditation processes. Knowledge of the reform appears to be primarily practical and reactive: researchers engage with the changes mainly when they face evaluation situations.

Despite this limited conceptual awareness, there appears to be a broad consensus across both groups of interviewees regarding the need to reform a system of research evaluation. However, this consensus coexists with significant tensions in the practical implementation of the reform, arising from the persistence of isolated metric-based evaluation practices, limited awareness of new evaluative frameworks, regulatory uncertainty, and institutional heterogeneity in the processes of adoption. From the perspective of policy makers, these challenges are largely interpreted as a reflection of the depth of the transformation required. Several interviewees emphasize that reforming research evaluation systems necessarily entails a broader cultural change in academic and evaluative practices.

In this context, our results suggest that the introduction of new principles of research evaluation does not entail the immediate replacement of one evaluative regime by another. Rather, the implementation of the reform appears to generate a hybrid evaluative regime characterized by tensions between different logics of scientific valuation. Based on the analysis of the interviews, in these preliminary results we explore two main tensions: (1) metrics versus qualitative judgement and (2) traditional merits versus alternative forms of recognition. We include a third section with tensions we have identified but have not yet explored to the fullest at the time of writing.

4.1 Metrics vs. qualitative judgement

One of the most recurrent tensions identified in the interviews concerns the role of quantitative indicators versus qualitative judgement in research evaluation processes. From the perspective of researchers, there is widespread criticism of the predominance of bibliometric indicators as the main criteria for evaluation. However, this criticism coexists with limited knowledge of how these indicators function in practice and of the alternative evaluative approaches proposed by the reform.

In the frequently cited debate on the subjectivity of evaluation, one interviewee argues that qualitative judgement, far from being the opposite of rigour, is the avenue to a professional, contextualised and informed assessment. In contrast to “highly quantitativist” frameworks that flatten singularities and reduce panels to “recording merits,” a qualitative approach restores the evaluator’s capacity to weigh the intrinsic value of each contribution and the circumstances of each case:

I believe that qualitative evaluation gives you a greater possibility of valuing singularities (...) Quantitativist systems are more like steamrollers (...) Because as an evaluator, if you have to evaluate within a very quantitativist framework, you may find yourself—and it has happened to me personally—having to write a negative report about someone you believe deserves accreditation, right? This dilemma (...) also arises in qualitative systems, but it appears more often in quantitativist ones. Because the

criteria for the evaluator's judgement are very limited... evaluators become measurers and recorders of merits, in a way, don't they? (...) I am not saying that evaluators (...) have a blank cheque to decide without criteria. That is not what I mean, but these are systems that do not allow for genuine expert appraisal. They are very formal. The guidelines are so extremely detailed that they do not allow for professional assessment, right? Personal judgements that are also professional (...) Of course there is always subjectivity, obviously, but I mean a judgement... they do not allow for professional judgement as much, and evaluators end up being mere recorders of merits. (A12, History, Professor)

Historically, this perception reflected a broader critique of highly formalized evaluation systems (Whitley, 2007), in which the role of evaluators becomes limited to registering predefined indicators, thereby constraining the possibility of exercising broader professional judgement.

Nevertheless, at the level of practical implementation, the introduction of qualitative evaluations also raises concerns. Several researchers note that such models may open greater space for evaluative discretion, raising concerns about potential subjectivity and the transparency of recruitment and promotion processes.

I think it's progress not to depend exclusively on papers—otherwise we live and die by that—but I also think it opens the door to subjectivity and to people getting positions not really on merit but because of who they are. So, it seems to me a positive evolution, but at the same time one that requires a lot of control to prevent abuses of power or the person prevailing over the CV. I'm not sure how that can be managed. (A19, Economics, doctoral student)

Beyond concerns about subjectivity, interviewees also highlight practical limitations related to the implementation of qualitative evaluations: increased time needed for in-depth review, greater workload for panels, and the need to develop clear criteria that ensure a degree of consistency across evaluators:

Encouraging good research—and not only the metrics that measure things which are not necessarily what we want to value in science—(...) from what we are seeing generates a lot of uncertainty among researchers. They are used, for better or for worse, to a set of rules of the game that we now want to change, but it's still not very clear how and towards what. (I13, policy maker)

In the interviews, the advantages of qualitative approaches are primarily associated with the possibility of recognizing singular academic trajectories, such as careers with interruptions, hybrid professional profiles, or forms of scientific production that fall outside conventional publication channels. Conversely, the risks mentioned relate to the absence of clear evaluation guidelines, variability across evaluators, and the increased costs associated with evaluation processes in terms of both time and institutional resources. Despite these concerns, there is a relatively widespread agreement among interviewees that bibliometric indicators should play a complementary role in research evaluation.

4.2 Traditional merits versus alternative forms of recognition

Both policy makers and researchers view positively the possibility of recognizing contributions beyond traditional academic publications, including aspects such as research impact, scientific leadership, or diverse types of research outputs. However, the introduction of these new criteria generates conceptual and methodological uncertainties. Several interviewees point to the ambiguity surrounding concepts such as “impact” or “leadership”, as well as the difficulties associated with measuring and evaluating them.

I think it is clear that our previous practices produced a structural bias, right? (...) There were—and still are—many activities by researchers that were not recognised at all, more to do with fostering structures and institutional practices that move the community forward, this more ‘common’ part; that was never valued. Or, for example, activities not only linked to the advance of knowledge but also to benefits to society at large. All that remained invisible and, therefore, unvalued, even though it is also part of the academic career. (I14, policy maker)

Both policy makers and researchers emphasize the potential of the reform to better capture the singularities of academic careers in a context where research trajectories are increasingly understood as non-linear and hybrid (Cañibano et al. 2024). Moreover, the reform is seen as offering opportunities to better accommodate disciplinary diversity, which interviewees describe as particularly challenging at the institutional level.

4.3 Other tensions

As previously mentioned, there are other tensions within the data that are interesting for our research question. Due to a lack of space, here we will briefly mention them. We expect to have them more developed by the time of the conference.

- Normative reform vs. practical implementation
- Standardising the researcher profile vs. contextualising trajectories
- Quantity vs. quality in the evaluation of scientific contributions
- Accountability vs. academic autonomy

All these tensions will be contextualized with the demographic characteristics of each interviewee regarding type of institution, discipline, job category, location of institution and gender. Moreover, some of the interviewees have played more than one role throughout their career (e.g. evaluator and the one being evaluated; researcher and afterwards policy maker), which we will consider when understanding the tensions in the implementation of CoARA.

5. Preliminary discussion and conclusions

Here we provide the preliminary results of one of the first studies that aims at understanding the current implementation of CoARA in one specific national context, the Spanish scientific system. Our findings highlight a gap between the normative consensus surrounding the need for reform and the complexities associated with its practical implementation. While both policy makers and researchers broadly support the objectives of the reform, its implementation generates significant tensions. In this regard, we have identified six main areas of tension: (1) Metrics vs. qualitative judgement, (2) Traditional merits versus alternative forms of recognition, (3) Normative reform vs. practical implementation, (4) Standardising the researcher profile vs. contextualising trajectories, (5) Quantity vs. quality in the evaluation of scientific contributions and (6) Accountability vs. academic autonomy.

Taken together, these tensions reflect broader structural dilemmas within science systems. They suggest that reforming research evaluation is not merely a technical adjustment, but rather a complex process involving deeper cultural and institutional transformations. Rather than replacing one evaluative system with another, the implementation of CoARA appears to generate a hybrid evaluative regime in which different logics of assessment coexist and sometimes conflict in practice. For the field of bibliometrics, these findings highlight the need to support institutions in navigating this transition by providing contextualized indicators that complement, rather than replace, expert judgement.

Overall, this ongoing study aims to provide insights for both policy makers and researchers on how CoARA is being interpreted and implemented across different institutional contexts. Throughout the interviews, some comments were recurrent, and given the diversity of the sample, we believe the results yield a preliminary picture of how the Spanish scientific community is dealing with the changes and challenges that signing CoARA implies. Further analysis will refine the identification of tensions and explore differences across disciplines and career stages, with results to be fully developed and presented at the conference.

Open science practices

The raw interview data cannot be shared publicly due to confidentiality and anonymization. However, the interview protocols and qualitative analysis codes will be made available alongside the study.

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Author contributions

Elvira González-Salmón: Data curation, formal analysis, investigation, software, visualization, writing - original draft

Carmen Corona Sobrino: Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, project administration, software, writing - review & editing

Zaida Chinchilla-Rodríguez: Conceptualization, funding acquisition, supervision, writing - review & editing

Competing interests

Authors of this research have no competing interests.

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